

Indigenous Traditional Ecological Knowledge as a Response to Climate Change and Conflict Mitigation in Tivland, Benue State, Nigeria

Nomishan, Terngu Sylvanus^a

^a Department of Archaeology and Museum Studies,
Federal University Lokoja, Nigeria.

terngu.nomishan@fulokoja.edu.ng

<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8275-3134>

^bEmeka E. Okonkwo, PhD

Department of Archaeology and Tourism,
University of Nigeria, Nsukka, Nigeria.

emeka.okonkwo@unn.edu.ng

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0652-7746>

^cBenjamin Wankaa Yio, PhD

Department of History and International Studies,
Federal University Lokoja, Kogi State, Nigeria.

benjamin.yio@fulokoja.edu.ng

<https://orcid.org/0009-0005-1022-5814>

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ABSTRACT

This research examines Indigenous Traditional Ecological Knowledge (ITEK) as a key response to climate change and conflict mitigation in Tivland, Benue State, Nigeria. This research explores how traditional environmental practices and cultural values can be applied as adaptive solutions to contemporary climate and social problems. The study adopts a qualitative approach, including ethnographic surveys in addition to key informant interviews and focus group discussions with farmers, elders, custodians of cultural traditions, and a review of documentary sources on indigenous knowledge systems. The findings of the study revealed that ecological knowledge among Tiv communities, through such practices as crop rotation, intercropping, sacred sites, seasonal farming calendars, land tenure systems, and communal ownership of resources, has contributed to greater environmental sustainability and ultimately reduced competition for scarce resources. These practices largely contribute to enhanced food security and community cohesion, consequently reducing climate-induced disputes or conflict over scarcity of resources. ITEK has, therefore, become a vital channel for the development of a culturally appropriate framework for climate change adaptation and peacebuilding. The study recommends that local communities hold opportunities to collaborate with relevant stakeholders and policy-makers in response to climate change and conflict mitigation.

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1.1. Introduction

The National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA) explains in 2024 that climate change is one of the long-term changes in average weather patterns that have come to define the Earth's local, regional and global climates. The world's climate symbolises the interconnected system of the sun, Earth, oceans, winds, precipitation, and snow, along with forests, deserts, savannahs, and human activities. The climate of a location, such as Tivland in Benue State, can be characterised by its rainfall patterns and temperature fluctuations throughout the year, among other similar factors (Shafer, 2023).

Climate change has emerged as one of the most urgent challenges of the 21st century, significantly impacting ecosystems, human communities, and global development (Weiskopf *et al.*, 2020). It involves long-term alterations in temperature, rainfall, and weather, primarily driven by human actions such as burning fossil fuels, deforestation, and unsustainable agricultural activities. Across the globe, these changes result in rising temperatures, melting ice caps, increased sea levels, extreme weather incidents, desertification, and loss of biodiversity. The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) in 2022 highlights that these effects threaten not only ecological balance but also intensify issues such as poverty, food insecurity, forced migration, and violent disputes over limited resources (Birkmann *et al.*, 2022; also see Adger *et al.*, 2014).

The World Health Organisation (WHO) stated in 2023 that climate change is directly linked to humanitarian crises, such as heatwaves, wildfires, floods, tropical storms, and hurricanes, which are becoming more frequent, severe, and widespread in the contemporary era. The report by WHO indicates that about 3.6 billion individuals currently reside in regions that are highly vulnerable to the effects of climate change. Between 2030 and 2050, it is projected that climate change will lead to around 250,000 additional deaths each year, attributed to undernutrition, malaria, diarrhoea, and heat stress alone. The estimated direct health-related damage costs (excluding expenses in health-influencing sectors such as agriculture, water, and sanitation) are projected to be between US\$2 billion and US\$4 billion annually by 2030. Regions with fragile health systems, primarily in developing nations, will struggle the most to manage without support for preparation and response. Decreasing greenhouse gas emissions through improved choices in transportation, food, and energy can yield significant health benefits, particularly by lowering air pollution levels (WHO, 2023).

In Africa, particularly in Nigeria, the effects of climate change are experienced more acutely due to a significant dependence on natural resources and livelihoods that are sensitive to climate fluctuations (Beyioku, 2016). In the northern part of Nigeria, there is a devastating impact of desertification on the environment, while rising sea levels are widely threatening the country's coastal regions. The Niger Delta's low-lying terrain and criss-cross of waterways has also created another climate change, making the area extremely vulnerable to flooding. In addition to being at risk of rising sea levels, it has produced dozens of victims of extreme oil pollution (Beyioku, 2016).

Additionally, in southern Nigeria, the impact of climate change was evident during the significant flooding that took place in 2012, where homes, agricultural fields, crops, personal properties, and even lives were lost. Furthermore, data released

approximately two years ago by the southwest zonal office of the National Emergency Management Agency (NEMA) indicates that over 5000 individuals were affected and 60 homes were destroyed due to a windstorm that occurred across four states in the southwestern region. In the southeastern area, the worsening effects of gully erosion have severely impacted numerous settlements and agricultural landscapes, resulting in increased poverty among local communities (Beyioku, 2016).

The scenario in Tivland State, often called the “food basket of Nigeria,” is similarly concerning as it becomes more susceptible due to its dependence on regular rainfall for farming activities (Ikpe and Omede, 2025). There have been slight changes in the seasonal patterns of rainfall in the state, as evidenced by signs such as inconsistent rainfall, extended periods of drought, flooding, land degradation, decreased crop yields, and a reduction in arable land. These environmental challenges have intensified disputes over land and water, particularly among farming communities and nomadic herders, resulting in conflicts that jeopardise food security, sustainable development, and social unity (Ikpe and Omede, 2025).

In light of this, there is a growing recognition of the need for alternative responses to climate change that are relevant to, and contextualised by, different situations and are more than simply stemming from a traditional scientific approach. Indigenous Traditional Ecological Knowledge (ITEK), based on centuries of Indigenous Knowledge and cultural adaptation, can offer usable and viable approaches to dealing with these local environmental issues, while providing indigenous avenues for conflict resolution to enhance community cohesion.

Benue State, which is prominent in food production in Nigeria because of its fertile soils and high agricultural productivity, has in recent decades become a major hotspot of violent conflicts. The most prominent of these are farmer–herder clashes and land disputes, which are increasingly tied to environmental stress, demographic pressures, and weak governance. Traditionally, pastoralism and farming coexisted through negotiated access to grazing routes and farmlands, but these arrangements have broken down due to population growth, urbanisation, climate change, and construction activities (Njoku, 2021).

This farmer–herder conflict is largely fuelled by changing climatic patterns, including desertification and drought in the northern regions of Nigeria, which pushes pastoralists further south into valuable farmlands in Benue State, causing an enormous strain on the farmers. Consequently, farmers usually accuse livestock owners of destroying crops and encroaching on farmlands (Onwunyi and Anekwe, 2020), while the livestock owners accuse farmers of protecting shrinking grazing landscapes and blocking migratory routes (Amnesty International, 2022). These disagreements between the farmers and herders usually lead to violent clashes, which result in high levels of casualties, damage to properties, and the displacement of communities. In some cases, these violent clashes take an ethnic and religious dimension, thereby making the issues even more complex to be resolved peacefully (Apenda, 2023; Nlewem and Akhagba, 2024).

Furthermore, land disputes have become a critical problem in Tivland. Traditionally, land is owned and managed communally via customary practices. However, population growth combined with the monetary worth of land has led to numerous disputes between families, communities, clans and even neighbouring communities in other states (Nomishan, 2026). Oftentimes, the declining effect of indigenous institutions is seen as one of the key reasons for the inability to sustainably resolve these conflicts. Also, the imposition of the Western legal system, along with the political administrative system, is considered to lack the capacity to resolve these disputes sustainably (Nomishan *et al.*, 2025). This is also because most land disputes are often politicised by elites who use them to their political advantage and exacerbate divisions in what would formerly be unified communities (Silva-Novo Sánchez *et al.*, 2025).

Thus, dealing effectively with these conflicts requires a comprehensive strategy that incorporates indigenous conflict resolution approaches with governmental systems, whilst also addressing the deep-seated causes related to climate change, land management and socio-economic disparities (Famugba and Adedayo, 2020). To this end, the ITEK is a key element of the needed response by the Tiv society to the dual challenges of climate change and conflict, especially as all the communities in the state depend largely on natural resources for livelihood.

Conceptual and Theoretical Framework

ITEK refers to the cumulative body of knowledge, practices, and beliefs that Indigenous and local communities develop over time through close interaction with their natural environment. It is knowledge passed down orally from generation to generation and is rooted in cultural traditions, spiritual values, and long-term observation of ecological processes. At its core, ITEK embodies how people understand, interpret, and respond to their environment for survival, resource management, and community well-being. It includes practices such as traditional farming systems, weather forecasting through natural signs, herbal medicine, soil and water conservation techniques, sacred groves for biodiversity protection, and conflict resolution mechanisms that ensure equitable access to natural resources.

Unlike modern scientific knowledge, which is often compartmentalised and experimental, ITEK is holistic; it integrates ecological, social, cultural, and spiritual dimensions of human-nature relationships. It is adaptive, meaning communities refine and adjust it over time in response to environmental changes. In the context of climate change, ITEK provides strategies for coping with droughts, floods, and soil degradation. In terms of conflict mitigation, it offers culturally embedded mechanisms, such as elders' mediation, communal land tenure systems, and customary laws, that reduce disputes over scarce resources. Thus, ITEK, in this sense, is not only a heritage of Indigenous communities but also a valuable knowledge system that complements modern science in addressing pressing issues of sustainability, resilience, and peacebuilding.

The most appropriate theory useful in this study is the entanglement theory. The Entanglement Theory was proposed by a British archaeologist, Ian Hodder, in 2012, emphasising the intricate web of interdependencies that exist between humans and things. It challenges the notion that humans merely use material objects or natural

resources for survival, arguing instead that humans and things are mutually dependent. Humans need things to live and give meaning to their social world, while things, in turn, require human attention, maintenance, and interpretation to remain functional and significant. This perspective underscores the inseparability of people, culture, and the material environment.

The core of the theory lies in four dependencies: humans depend on things, things depend on humans, things depend on other things, and humans depend on other humans through things. These relationships create entanglements that shape human history and everyday life. In agricultural societies such as the Tiv, land, crops, rivers, and tools are not just resources but active participants in shaping livelihoods, social structures, and conflicts. Climate change intensifies these entanglements by destabilising the balance between people and their environment.

Communities in Tivland are deeply entangled with the environment through farming, herding, fishing, and forest use. When rainfall patterns shift or soils degrade due to climate change, the entanglements between humans and land become strained. Farmers' reliance on fertile soils, herders' dependence on pasture, and communities' need for water all illustrate the interconnectedness that, when disrupted, contributes to tension and conflict. Thus, entanglement theory provides a lens to see how ecological stress translates into social unrest.

Farmer–herder clashes in Tivland can be explained through entanglement theory as disputes arising from overlapping dependencies on shared ecological resources. Farmers depend on land for cultivation, while herders depend on the same land for grazing. Climate change, by reducing resource availability, magnifies the entanglements and increases the likelihood of conflict. Indigenous knowledge systems, however, contain mechanisms, such as communal land management and rotational resource use, that help to navigate and rebalance these entanglements peacefully.

Indigenous Traditional Ecological Knowledge itself is a product of entanglement. It embodies centuries of accumulated wisdom derived from close interaction with land, rivers, plants, and animals. Practices such as crop rotation, sacred groves, and traditional rainmaking rituals demonstrate how cultural beliefs and ecological realities are entangled. In Tivland, ITEK functions not only as a survival strategy but also as a cultural framework for managing interdependence with nature and preventing conflicts that arise from resource competition.

Entanglement theory also highlights the interconnectedness of different knowledge systems. Modern scientific ecological knowledge (SEK) and ITEK are entangled in ways that can be either complementary or conflicting. In addressing climate change in Tivland, policies that integrate indigenous practices with modern scientific methods reflect a recognition of these entanglements. For instance, combining traditional weather forecasting with satellite data provides more reliable predictions that help both farmers and herders plan resource use, reducing the likelihood of disputes.

Applying entanglement theory to this study shows that ITEK is valuable precisely because it manages these webs of interdependencies. Indigenous institutions, such as councils of elders, traditional mediators, and traditional religious priests, regulate access to these resources and foster cooperation. By mediating entanglements between

people and the environment, between different groups, and between ecological systems, ITEK reduces tensions and promotes resilience. This makes it a crucial tool for both climate adaptation and conflict mitigation in Tivland. This theory applies well in this study because it provides a framework for understanding the deep and complex ties between people, resources, and knowledge systems. Climate change and conflicts in Tivland cannot be fully understood without recognising these interdependencies. By foregrounding entanglements, the study highlights the importance of ITEK in sustaining ecological balance, preventing conflicts, and fostering peace. Ultimately, entanglement theory underscores that sustainable solutions must address the intertwined nature of human–environment relations.

1.2. Research Methods

This study employed a qualitative research design to understand how ITEK provides a means to adapt to Climate Change as well as Mitigate Conflict in Tivland, Benue State, Nigeria. This is because it facilitates and paves the way for deeper insight into Indigenous Knowledge Systems, Cultural Practices, and the lived experiences of the Indigenous People. Ethnographic Fieldwork, including in-depth interviews, Focus Group Discussions (FGDs) and Key Informants Interviews (KIIs) with Farmers, Pastoralists, Community Elders, Traditional Leaders and Custodians of Indigenous knowledge were carried out to elicit the data from the purposefully selected study participants from selected communities in Tivland.

This study employed a purposive sampling technique, which ensured that informed participants were selected due to their knowledge and experiences concerning subject of the study. In addition, participant observation was employed to document farming practices, land-use patterns, cultural rituals, and conflict mediation processes as they occur within their natural socio-cultural context. The informants in the study were selected from various Local Government Areas (LGAs) in Tivland State, including Gboko, Gwer-East, Katsina-Ala, Konshisha, Kwande, Makurdi, Ushongo, and Vandeikya. A total of 162 participants were interviewed. Out of this number, 102 participants were males, while 60 were females. This was because men are more involved in the practices of interest to this study than women.

Relevant academic journals, books, and government reports regarding climate change, traditional ecological knowledge systems, and conflict resolution provided the secondary data for this study. The data collected were analysed thematically, utilising content and narrative analysis to identify recurring patterns, meanings, and relationships between climate change impacts, indigenous ecological practices, and conflict mitigation strategies. The interpretation of findings was guided by entanglement theory, which provided a framework for understanding the interconnectedness between people, ecological resources, and indigenous knowledge systems. Ethical considerations, including informed consent, confidentiality, and respect for cultural norms, were strictly observed throughout the research process to ensure the credibility and integrity of the study.

1.3. Results and Discussion

Climate Change and Its Manifestations in Tivland

The Tiv society has in recent decades experienced a steady rise in temperature, which affects both the natural ecosystem and human livelihoods (Agbo and Ikpe, 2025). Increased heat intensity shortens the growing season of crops such as yams, maize, and rice, while also reducing soil moisture content. This warming trend has led to higher evapotranspiration rates, making farmlands more vulnerable to dryness and crop failure. For rural farmers, who depend largely on rain-fed agriculture, rising temperatures translate into reduced yields, food insecurity, and heightened pressure on already scarce resources (Agbo and Ikpe, 2025).

Rainfall patterns in Tivland have become increasingly unpredictable, with delayed onset, early cessation, and irregular distribution of rain. In some years, prolonged dry spells occur during critical growing periods, resulting in droughts that devastate crops. Farmers who traditionally rely on indigenous knowledge to predict weather are finding it harder to adapt to these irregular patterns, leading to mismatched planting seasons and crop losses. Droughts not only reduce food availability but also force households to diversify livelihoods, sometimes pushing young people into migration and creating competition over limited resources (Oche and Dzenda, 2024).

While droughts affect some areas, other parts of Tivland suffer from recurrent flooding, particularly along the Benue River and its floodplains. Intense rainfall events wash away topsoil, destroy crops, displace communities, and damage infrastructure. Flooding accelerates soil degradation by eroding fertile farmlands and reducing their long-term productivity. In addition, gully erosion in parts of the state worsens land degradation, making it increasingly difficult for farmers to sustain subsistence agriculture. These environmental stresses contribute to cycles of poverty and displacement for rural households.

The manifestations of climate change in Tivland directly affect farming and livelihoods, given that over 70% of the population depends on agriculture. Reduced productivity from droughts, floods, and soil degradation undermines food security, increases poverty levels, and intensifies competition over fertile land and water. This competition often escalates into conflicts, particularly between farmers and herders struggling over shrinking resources. Furthermore, the loss of agricultural income limits families' ability to afford education, healthcare, and other basic needs, perpetuating cycles of vulnerability. Thus, the socio-economic implications of climate change in Tivland extend beyond farming to encompass peace, security, and overall human well-being (Anthony, 2015).

In the context of this study, climate pressures such as erratic rainfall, prolonged droughts, flooding, and soil degradation directly affect the availability and quality of natural resources in Tivland (Bolarin *et al.*, 2022). As an agrarian society, the Tiv people rely heavily on land, water, and vegetation for farming and livestock rearing (Halima and Edoja, 2026). When climate change reduces agricultural productivity, depletes grazing fields, or dries up water sources, it heightens competition over these already limited resources. Farmers struggle to secure fertile land for cultivation, while herders

extend grazing routes in search of pasture and water. These overlapping dependencies create tensions, as both groups depend on the same ecological spaces for survival.

Resource-based conflicts in Tivland, particularly between farmers and herders, are therefore closely tied to climate pressures that destabilise traditional patterns of resource use (Eke *et al.*, 2025). As natural resources become scarcer, disputes over farmland boundaries, grazing corridors, and water points intensify, often escalating into violent confrontations. ITEK, however, offers coping mechanisms such as communal land tenure systems, rotational resource use, and mediation by elders, which help in reducing the frequency and severity of these conflicts (Nomishan *et al.*, 2025). Thus, the relationship between climate pressures and resource-based conflicts underscores the importance of ITEK as both an adaptive strategy to environmental stress and a framework for conflict mitigation.

Sources and Practices of Indigenous Traditional Ecological Knowledge in Tivland

Agriculture is the backbone of the Tiv economy, and ITEK is deeply embedded in their farming systems. The Tiv communities rely on shifting cultivation (Gumh, 2019), where farmland is alternated over a period of 4 to 6 years to allow soil regeneration and prevent nutrient depletion. Elsewhere in Tanzania, “farmers practising some form of shifting cultivation, the normal cycle consists of 4-6 years of cultivation followed by 1-3 years of natural fallow, the very limited land availability precluding longer periods of soil regeneration. Under these circumstances, the natural vegetation never reverts back to grassland/woodland” (Nshubemuki, 1985, p. 149). According to information obtained through a FGD in Ushongo (Focus Group Discussion, 29 December 2025), mixed cropping, such as the combination of yams, maize, beans, and cassava, is another adaptive practice that reduces risks of crop failure, ensures food security, and enhances soil fertility through complementary nutrient cycles. In riverine areas, farmers use traditional irrigation methods, like channelling streams or using earthen basins to trap water, which sustain crops during dry seasons and reduce dependence on unpredictable rainfall.

ITEK also manifests in the sustainable management of forests, water bodies, and grazing lands. Selected landscapes, such as sacred groves in locations like Turan, Ikyurav-Ya, Ishangev-Ya, Kunav, Mbayegh, among others, are preserved as spiritually significant spaces where cutting trees or hunting is forbidden, indirectly serving as biodiversity conservation zones. In Tivland, various communities maintain communal forest rules, which regulate access to firewood, timber, and medicinal plants to prevent overexploitation. The practice of fallowing, leaving farmland unused for some years, is another indigenous method that allows soil to regain fertility and reduces land degradation (interview, 29 December 2025). These practices reflect an ecological ethic that balances human needs with environmental regeneration.

Local communities in Tivland use indigenous methods of weather forecasting to predict climatic patterns and guide agricultural activities. Animal behaviour, such as the movement of ants, frogs, or birds, is interpreted as a sign of approaching rain. Similarly, plant cycles, like the flowering of certain trees (for example, the shea butter tree), indicate seasonal changes. Changes in wind patterns and cloud formations are also used to anticipate rainfall intensity or storms. These indicators, accumulated over

generations, provide early warning systems that help farmers and herders plan for planting, harvesting, or migration, especially in the absence of modern meteorological data (Focus Group Discussion, 29 December 2025).

In addition to ecological knowledge, indigenous systems in Tivland provide frameworks for managing conflicts, especially those linked to natural resources. Elders act as mediators, drawing on cultural authority and wisdom to resolve disputes between farmers and herders or among community members. Communal land tenure systems, which regulate ownership and access to farmland, help prevent disputes by ensuring equitable distribution and clarifying rights of use. These practices reduce competition over land and resources while reinforcing collective responsibility for environmental stewardship.

Cultural traditions and festivals in Tivland also play an important role in promoting social cohesion and peace. Annual cultural festivals, such as the Yam Festival, bring communities together, fostering unity and dialogue. During such events, disputes may be settled informally, and rituals are performed to renew communal harmony. These practices strengthen inter-group relations, discourage hostility, and reinforce shared values of cooperation in managing ecological resources. Thus, cultural traditions serve as both ecological and conflict-mitigation mechanisms.

The sources and practices of ITEK in Tivland demonstrate a holistic approach to human–environment relations. From sustainable farming and forest management to local forecasting and conflict resolution, these practices reflect a deep understanding of ecological systems and social dynamics. Importantly, they are not isolated activities but interconnected strategies that simultaneously secure livelihoods, conserve resources, and foster peace. In the context of climate change and rising conflicts, such knowledge provides practical lessons for adaptation, resilience, and sustainable coexistence.

ITEK as a Response to Climate Change in Tivland

ITEK emphasises flexible farming methods that allow communities to withstand climatic uncertainties. Farmers practice mixed cropping, intercropping, and crop rotation to spread risks, improve soil fertility, and ensure food availability even when some crops fail. Early and late-maturing crop varieties are also cultivated to adapt to unpredictable rainfall patterns. Shifting cultivation and the planting of drought-tolerant species, such as millet and sorghum, further demonstrate adaptive strategies that reduce vulnerability to climate-induced food shortages.

Soil fertility management is a critical part of ITEK. Communities in Tivland and other regions use organic manure, crop residues, and fallow systems to replenish soil nutrients naturally. Terracing, contour ridges, and mulching are employed to reduce erosion and maintain soil moisture, especially in flood-prone and drought-affected areas. These indigenous practices are sustainable, cost-effective, and suited to local ecological conditions, offering resilience against the soil degradation often worsened by climate change.

Indigenous communities also employ techniques to manage scarce water resources. Traditional irrigation systems, such as small earthen canals and water harvesting in ponds, ensure crop survival during dry spells. Farmers also plant trees along riverbanks

to prevent siltation and maintain water flow. In some areas, communities rely on sacred water sources that are protected through cultural taboos, ensuring their preservation for agriculture and domestic use. These methods demonstrate how ITEK contributes to adaptive water management in the face of climate variability.

Biodiversity is central to ITEK because diverse ecosystems ensure resilience to environmental shocks. Communities conserve biodiversity through sacred groves, community forests, and taboos against indiscriminate hunting or tree cutting. Seed preservation and exchange systems safeguard indigenous crop varieties that are often more climate-resilient than exotic species. By protecting medicinal plants, wild food species, and traditional livestock breeds, ITEK helps sustain genetic diversity, which is vital for long-term adaptation to climate change.

ITEK also includes indigenous forecasting systems that predict weather patterns and help communities prepare for climate extremes. Farmers observe natural indicators such as wind direction, animal behaviour, insect movements, the flowering of certain plants, and star positions to predict rainfall or drought. These forecasts guide planting schedules, harvesting, and migration decisions for both farmers and pastoralists. Although not infallible, these systems have historically enabled communities to minimise risks associated with climate variability.

ITEK and Conflict Mitigation in Tivland

Indigenous Traditional Ecological Knowledge (ITEK) is not only about ecological practices but also about the cultural mechanisms that regulate social relations, resource use, and conflict management. In Tivland, where climate change has intensified resource competition between farmers, herders, and other groups, ITEK plays a significant role in mitigating conflicts. It provides time-tested systems of peacebuilding, land management, dialogue, and cultural values that promote coexistence and solidarity. These indigenous strategies are rooted in communal traditions and continue to serve as alternative frameworks for sustaining peace in the face of modern challenges.

Traditional institutions, particularly councils of elders, chiefs, and clan heads, hold significant authority in conflict resolution in Tiv communities. These leaders are considered custodians of wisdom and moral authority, drawing on cultural values and collective memory to mediate disputes. When conflicts arise, such as boundary disputes, farmer–herder clashes, or disagreements over land, elders convene meetings where dialogue and reconciliation are prioritised. Their involvement ensures that settlements are culturally legitimate, widely respected, and binding on the parties, thereby reducing the recurrence of violence.

Elders not only mediate but also invoke cultural sanctions or blessings that reinforce agreements. For instance, peace accords may be sealed through shared meals, libation rituals, or oath-taking, which are culturally binding. These practices strengthen trust and accountability, ensuring that disputing parties abide by resolutions. In many Tiv communities of Benue State, the presence of respected elders in peace processes discourages aggression and channels grievances into constructive dialogue, illustrating the strong role of ITEK in peacebuilding.

Land in many parts of Tiv society is traditionally regarded as communal rather than individual property, with access governed by customary laws. These regulations ensure that land is shared equitably and sustainably managed, preventing monopolisation and reducing potential for disputes. The practice of rotational farming, collective land clearing, and shared grazing rights reflects ecological wisdom aimed at balancing human needs with environmental sustainability. By ensuring that land remains accessible to all community members, indigenous land tenure systems help to minimise competition and conflicts that often stem from scarcity.

Dialogue, facilitated by customary laws, is a cornerstone of ITEK-based conflict resolution in Tiv society. Disputes are often resolved in public forums where transparency and collective participation are emphasised. Customary laws, which embody moral and cultural principles, regulate behaviour and prescribe sanctions for offenders. These laws cover issues such as land encroachment, theft, and violence, and their enforcement by community leaders creates a sense of justice and accountability. The emphasis on dialogue ensures that conflicts are de-escalated before they spiral into violence.

Rituals play an important role in reinforcing peace agreements and restoring harmony between conflicting parties. Rituals may include symbolic gestures such as the exchange of gifts, animal sacrifices, or communal feasts that signify reconciliation. These practices are not mere ceremonies but powerful cultural tools that bind individuals and groups to peaceful coexistence. In some cases, the fear of spiritual retribution for violating ritual covenants acts as a deterrent to future conflict. Through such practices, ITEK embeds peacebuilding within the spiritual and cultural fabric of the community.

ITEK in Tivland also fosters cultural values that underpin peaceful relations, including solidarity, cooperation, and environmental stewardship. Agricultural activities such as cooperative farming (known locally as *Ihyumbe* among the Tiv) encourage collective labour and strengthen bonds between families and clans (Focus Group Discussion, 29 December 2025). Similarly, festivals and cultural ceremonies promote unity and remind communities of their shared heritage. These values cultivate a spirit of cooperation rather than competition, reducing the likelihood of conflicts over resources while simultaneously encouraging sustainable environmental practices.

Challenges to the Application of ITEK in Tivland

One of the major challenges to the application of ITEK in Tivland is its gradual erosion due to modernisation, globalisation, and religious shifts. Many traditional ecological practices, such as the use of sacred groves for biodiversity protection or ritual-based rainmaking, are being abandoned as communities embrace modern agricultural technologies, global cultural values, and new religious teachings that often dismiss indigenous practices as “pagan” or outdated. This erosion weakens the cultural foundations of ITEK and limits its relevance among younger generations who are increasingly oriented towards westernised methods of living and problem-solving.

The rising population in Tivland has intensified pressure on land and natural resources, which undermines the effectiveness of ITEK-based practices. Traditional farming systems such as shifting cultivation and fallowing, which depend on abundant land to allow soil regeneration, are becoming impractical as population growth reduces

available farmland. Similarly, herders face shrinking grazing areas, leading to encroachments on farmlands and escalating conflicts. The inability to practice ITEK effectively in such constrained spaces highlights the tension between population dynamics and traditional ecological systems.

A further challenge is the lack of recognition of ITEK within formal climate adaptation and conflict resolution policies at the state and national levels. Government programs and development initiatives often prioritise scientific knowledge and modern technologies, sidelining indigenous practices that have sustained communities for centuries. This exclusion not only diminishes the value of ITEK but also creates a disconnect between local communities and formal governance structures, making adaptation and peacebuilding efforts less effective and less inclusive.

Another significant challenge is the generational gap in the transmission of ITEK. In the past, indigenous knowledge was passed orally from elders to the youth through storytelling, apprenticeship, and participation in cultural practices. Today, the younger generation often prioritises formal education, urban migration, and modern lifestyles, which leaves little room for learning traditional practices. As a result, vital knowledge about weather forecasting, medicinal plants, soil conservation, and conflict resolution traditions risks being lost with the older generation.

Integrating ITEK with Modern Approaches in Tivland

ITEK and modern scientific knowledge are often seen as separate systems, yet both can complement one another when properly integrated. In Tivland, farmers already apply indigenous techniques such as intercropping, organic manure use, and local weather forecasting, while modern science provides improved seeds, soil analysis, and satellite-based climate predictions. A synergy between the two enables communities to benefit from the strengths of each system: indigenous methods ensure sustainability, cultural acceptance, and low cost, while scientific approaches offer precision, innovation, and scalability. Together, they provide more resilient strategies to cope with climate change and reduce tensions over scarce resources.

For example, blending traditional mixed cropping with modern soil fertility management helps farmers in Tivland maintain soil health while increasing yields. Similarly, indigenous knowledge of local plant behaviour can be combined with meteorological data to develop more reliable early warning systems for droughts and floods. Such hybrid approaches reduce vulnerability to climate shocks, making both farmers and herders less likely to engage in conflict over diminishing land and water resources. By recognising the validity of ITEK, science becomes more accessible and relevant to local communities.

To institutionalise this synergy, clear policy frameworks are needed to recognise ITEK as a legitimate and valuable knowledge system. Policies should promote the documentation of indigenous practices, integrate them into formal climate adaptation plans, and encourage their inclusion in conflict resolution frameworks. Education curricula in Tiv society could incorporate ITEK alongside modern agricultural science, ensuring younger generations learn both systems. Furthermore, peacebuilding policies should formalise the role of traditional authorities and elders in mediation, recognising their cultural legitimacy in resolving disputes linked to environmental stress.

The successful integration of ITEK and modern approaches requires multi-stakeholder collaboration. The government can provide legal backing and funding for ITEK-based initiatives, while NGOs can support training, capacity building, and documentation of indigenous practices. Local communities remain central as custodians of ITEK, ensuring practices are culturally grounded and sustainable. Collaborative platforms involving all three actors can foster dialogue, joint planning, and knowledge exchange, ensuring that both scientific and indigenous approaches reinforce each other rather than compete.

1.4. Conclusion and Recommendations

This study has demonstrated that ITEK remains a vital tool for addressing the dual challenges of climate change and conflict in Tivland. The findings revealed that local communities possess rich ecological knowledge developed over centuries of interaction with their environment. Practices such as mixed cropping, shifting cultivation, the use of organic manure, preservation of sacred groves, and traditional irrigation systems provide practical, cost-effective strategies for sustaining livelihoods in the face of climate variability. These adaptive practices enhance agricultural productivity, conserve biodiversity, and strengthen resilience against droughts, floods, and soil degradation.

Beyond ecological benefits, the research found that ITEK contributes significantly to conflict mitigation in Tivland. Traditional institutions, councils of elders, and communal land tenure systems play crucial roles in regulating resource use, mediating disputes, and promoting reconciliation between conflicting groups. Through dialogue, cultural rituals, and communal values of cooperation, ITEK-based conflict resolution mechanisms address resource-based disputes and reduce the likelihood of violent clashes, particularly between farmers and herders. These findings illustrate that ITEK is not only an environmental management system but also a peacebuilding framework deeply rooted in cultural identity.

The study underscores that ITEK is highly relevant in promoting sustainable climate adaptation. Local forecasting systems, biodiversity conservation practices, and adaptive farming strategies ensure that communities remain responsive to shifting weather patterns. Unlike externally imposed interventions, ITEK provides solutions that are culturally acceptable, affordable, and ecologically sound. Its holistic nature, integrating ecological, cultural, and spiritual dimensions, makes it a more comprehensive approach to sustainability compared to purely scientific models, which often overlook local realities.

Equally, the peacebuilding relevance of ITEK cannot be overstated. The farmer–herder conflict, land disputes, and other resource-related clashes in Tivland are effectively mediated through indigenous conflict resolution methods. These methods reinforce social cohesion, accountability, and trust, making peace settlements more legitimate and enduring. By embedding environmental stewardship within cultural norms and moral sanctions, ITEK strengthens communal solidarity and reduces the escalation of conflicts triggered by ecological stress.

Despite its value, ITEK faces significant threats from modernisation, population pressures, and declining intergenerational transmission. To safeguard and maximise its potential, there is a pressing need for systematic recognition, documentation, and

preservation of indigenous practices. Policymakers, scholars, and development practitioners must acknowledge ITEK as a legitimate body of knowledge rather than dismiss it as outdated. Documentation efforts, combined with awareness campaigns, will ensure that younger generations inherit and refine these practices, keeping them relevant in addressing contemporary challenges.

Finally, this study calls for the integration of ITEK into formal climate adaptation and conflict mitigation strategies in Tivland. Collaborative frameworks that merge indigenous knowledge with modern scientific approaches will provide more robust solutions to ecological and social challenges. Government agencies, NGOs, and community leaders must work together to institutionalise ITEK within policy frameworks, agricultural programs, and peacebuilding initiatives. By doing so, Tivland can harness its cultural heritage not only as a survival strategy but as a pathway to long-term sustainability, resilience, and peaceful coexistence.

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